

Study of the effectiveness of soil purification from petroleum products using humic substances

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One of the promising approaches in this context is the use of humic substances — natural macromolecules with high sorption capacity, capable of binding heavy metals and organic pollutants. In addition, humates stimulate the development of soil microflora and contribute to the restoration of the humus layer. Studies have shown that the combination of humates with active microorganisms significantly increases the efficiency of oil-contaminated soil remediation [1].

Table 1. Results of the mass fraction of petroleum products in the soil on days 5, 30, 60, and 90 of the experiment after treatment with potassium humate-based biopreparations

Model name	Mass fraction of petroleum products in soil sample, mg / kg, 5 days	Mass fraction of petroleum products in soil sample, mg / kg, 30 days	Mass fraction of petroleum products in soil sample, mg / kg, 60 days	Mass fraction of petroleum products in soil sample, mg / kg, 90 days	Content of petroleum products, %	Degree of purification, %
Original oil contaminated soil	86.528	86.528	86.528	86.528	100	0
Basic potassium humate 50%	83.600	61.300	17.600	12.300	2.62	85.78
Potassium humate+Si 50%	86.900	64.300	20.300	15.200	3.96	82.43
Potassium humate+NPK 50%	85.200	63.000	19.600	16.400	5.21	81.05

Figure 1. Determination of petroleum products in soil

After 90 days, the content of petroleum products significantly decreased. The highest effect was shown by basic potassium humate (purification — 85.78%). Compositions with Si and NPK provided 82.43% and 81.05%, respectively. This confirms the potential of humic substances for the remediation of contaminated soils.

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References

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